
Curriculum Development in Madrasah Education: A Comparative Study with Mainstream Education in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Bangladesh's education system has historically included madrasahs. Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs shape the lives and futures of numerous students. However, rapid global change has made Madrasah education reform necessary. This dissertation examines Bangladeshi Madrasah education's history, differences between Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs, problems, and prospects. The research shows a complicated educational landscape where religious teachings coexist with modern academia. This study found English, maths, and ICT competency gaps between Madrasah and mainstream students. Poor teacher support, faculty skills mismatches, and large course loads contribute to this gap. This educational disparity might hurt Madrasah students' employability and academic performance. Religious-only Qawmi Madrasahs are less prepared for a quickly changing world. These schools are unwilling to teach non-religious courses, restricting student exposure to other viewpoints. Restrictions on reading and contact have curtailed kids' outside world exposure. In contrast, Alia Madrasahs balance religious knowledge with specialised subjects. This approach is excellent, but Alia Madrasahs confront resource limits, ageing infrastructure, and dwindling enrolment. These obstacles make Bangladeshi Madrasah education dubious. The article stresses the need for reform to help Madrasahs fulfil modern needs. Madrasah authorities, the government, and society must adapt, innovate, and invest in these institutions. This study concludes that curriculum development is key to improving Madrasah education. Students can better handle future issues by balancing religious and modern studies, encouraging critical thinking, and problem-solving. This comprehensive article examines Madrasah education in Bangladesh and highlights future difficulties and potential. It encourages Madrasahs to adapt to the changing educational scene to improve their students' and nation's future.

Keywords: Curriculum Development, Madrasah Education, Madrasah Curriculum, Bangladeshi Madrasah Curriculum

1 Introduction

1.1 Background information on Madrasah education in Bangladesh

Madrasah education in Bangladesh has a rich historical legacy dating back centuries [1] [2]. These Islamic educational institutions play a significant role in shaping the religious and academic landscape of the country.

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Madrasahs are known for providing students with a strong foundation in Islamic studies, including Quranic teachings, Hadith, Arabic literature, and religious jurisprudence [3] [4]. Two primary types of madrasahs exist in Bangladesh: Alia Madrasahs and Qawmi Madrasahs. Alia Madrasahs, unlike their Qawmi counterparts, operate within state-defined parameters and are subject to administrative oversight. They offer a curriculum that includes government-approved subjects alongside religious studies. Qawmi Madrasahs, on the other hand, are privately run and follow their own curriculum, with a predominant focus on religious knowledge [5] [6]. The coexistence of these two distinct forms of madrasah education has led to various educational challenges and disparities in the country. These challenges range from differences in proficiency levels in English and mathematics to debates about the recognition and equivalence of Qawmi madrasah degrees in the national education system.

1.2 Purpose and significance of the study

The purpose of this study is to conduct a comparative analysis of curriculum development in Madrasah education, with a specific focus on Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs, in the context of mainstream education in Bangladesh. By exploring the curriculum, challenges, and impact of both systems, this research aims to shed light on the educational disparities and opportunities within the country.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to inform educational policymakers, institutions, and stakeholders about the strengths and weaknesses of the Madrasah education system in Bangladesh. It also aims to address the critical issues faced by students and graduates of Madrasahs, especially regarding their proficiency in subjects like English, mathematics, and ICT. Additionally, the study examines the socio-political implications of Madrasah education in the country, contributing to a broader understanding of its role in shaping Bangladesh's educational landscape.

1.3 Research questions and objectives

The study addresses several key research questions:

1. What are the core differences between the curriculum development in Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs in Bangladesh?
2. How do these differences impact students' proficiency in subjects such as English and Mathematics?
3. What are the challenges faced by Madrasah students and faculty in terms of curriculum development and implementation?
4. What are the implications of these disparities for students' employability and socioeconomic mobility?
5. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance curriculum development and bridge the educational gaps in Madrasah education?

The objectives of this study include:

- To analyze the curriculum structures of Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs.
- To evaluate the proficiency levels of Madrasah students in subjects like English and Mathematics.
- To identify the challenges faced by students and faculty in the curriculum implementation.
- To assess the impact of these challenges on students' employability.
- To provide recommendations for curriculum development and improvement in Madrasah education.

This paper is structured as follows:

1. In Section II, we delve into a comprehensive literature review, providing an overview of Madrasah education in Bangladesh, the challenges it faces, government policies, and its socio-political impact.
2. Section III presents a comparative analysis, highlighting the differences in curriculum development between Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs and their consequences on students' skills and exposure.
3. In Section IV, we discuss the challenges faced by Madrasah students and educators, including socioeconomic factors, stigma, and resource constraints.
4. Section V explores recommendations for enhancing curriculum development and addressing the educational gaps in Madrasah education.

5. Finally, Section VI offers a conclusion, summarizing key findings, insights, and the future outlook for Madrasah education in Bangladesh.

With this structured framework, we embark on a journey to explore and understand the intricate dynamics of Madrasah education and its role in shaping the future of students and society in Bangladesh.

2 Literature Review

The roots of Madrasah education in the Bengal region can be traced to the medieval period when scholars and religious leaders sought to disseminate Islamic knowledge [7] [8]. The establishment of Madrasahs gained momentum during the Mughal Empire's rule in the Indian subcontinent [9]. These centers of learning aimed to provide a comprehensive education in Islamic theology, jurisprudence, philosophy, and other religious sciences. Over time, Madrasahs evolved and adapted to the changing socio-political landscape of the region. However, it was during the British colonial period that Madrasah education in Bangladesh faced significant challenges [10]. The British administration introduced a western-style education system that posed a direct competition to traditional Madrasahs. Despite these challenges, Madrasahs continued to thrive, preserving Islamic knowledge and values. After gaining independence from British rule and becoming East Pakistan (later Bangladesh), the government recognized the importance of Madrasah education. Efforts were made to modernize and integrate Madrasahs into the national education system. This led to the emergence of two distinct categories of Madrasahs: Alia and Qawmi. These two systems coexist, each with its unique characteristics, curriculum, and governance.

Alia Madrasahs:

- Alia Madrasahs are government-regulated and funded institutions that follow a standardized curriculum that integrates both religious and modern subjects [11].
- The curriculum of Alia Madrasahs includes subjects such as Arabic, Islamic studies, Bengali, English, Mathematics, Science, and Social Studies.
- Alia Madrasahs are subject to oversight by the Bangladesh Madrasah Education Board (BMEB) and follow the guidelines set by the National Education Policy.
- Graduates of Alia Madrasahs receive certifications such as Dakhil and Alim, which are recognized by the government and enable them to pursue higher education in universities.

Qawmi Madrasahs:

- Qawmi Madrasahs, on the other hand, are privately run institutions that primarily focus on religious education and follow a traditional curriculum [12].
- The curriculum of Qawmi Madrasahs is heavily centered on religious texts, including the Quran, Hadith (sayings and actions of Prophet Muhammad), Fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence), and Tafsir (Quranic exegesis).
- Unlike Alia Madrasahs, Qawmi Madrasahs are not subject to government regulation or oversight in terms of curriculum or administration.
- Graduates of Qawmi Madrasahs receive religious degrees, with the most prestigious being the Dawra-e-Hadith, equivalent to a Master's degree, although it is not recognized by the government for employment in the public sector.

These two systems of Madrasah education in Bangladesh coexist, providing educational opportunities to a significant portion of the population. However, they also face distinct challenges and have varying impacts on students' skills, employability, and integration into the broader society.

2.1 Educational challenges in Madrasahs

Madrasah education in Bangladesh faces a multitude of educational challenges that have significant implications for students' academic and socio-economic outcomes. These challenges encompass a wide range of issues, from disparities in proficiency in key subjects like English and Mathematics to the formulation of curricula that primarily focus on religious knowledge [4]. In this section, we will delve into these challenges in detail, shedding light on their consequences and potential solutions. One of the most glaring challenges faced by Madrasah students in Bangladesh is the disparity in proficiency in subjects like English and Mathematics compared to their

counterparts in mainstream schools. Various studies and reports have consistently shown that Madrasah students lag behind in these critical subjects [13], hampering their ability to compete in the job market and pursue higher education effectively. This proficiency gap can be attributed to several factors, including the curriculum's heavy emphasis on religious studies at the expense of science and mathematics. While Alia Madrasahs offer a curriculum that integrates both religious and modern subjects, the quality of instruction and resources for these modern subjects often falls short. In contrast, Qawmi Madrasahs primarily focus on religious knowledge, leaving students ill-prepared for academic and professional challenges that require proficiency in English and Mathematics [14]. To address this challenge, there is a pressing need to revamp the curriculum and pedagogical approaches in Madrasahs. Modernizing the teaching methods, providing adequate training to teachers, and investing in resources for subjects like Mathematics and English are essential steps in narrowing the proficiency gap.

Mismatch of skills among faculty

The educational challenges in Madrasahs are further compounded by a significant mismatch of skills among the faculty. Madrasah teachers often lack the qualifications and training required to effectively teach modern subjects, especially in Alia Madrasahs, where both religious and secular subjects are taught. Many teachers in Madrasahs have received their education in traditional religious studies, making them ill-equipped to teach subjects like Mathematics, Science, and English. This skills gap among the teaching staff directly affects the quality of education provided to students. To address this issue, comprehensive teacher training programs are essential [15]. These programs should focus on enhancing teachers' proficiency in modern subjects and equipping them with effective pedagogical techniques [16]. Additionally, incentives for qualified teachers to join Madrasahs and mentorship programs can help bridge the skills gap among faculty.

Heavy course loads and lack of teacher support

Madrasah students often contend with heavy course loads that can be overwhelming, especially given the focus on religious studies. The demanding nature of the curriculum leaves little room for students to explore co-curricular activities or develop critical thinking skills [17]. Furthermore, the lack of adequate teacher support exacerbates the issue. In many cases, students struggle to grasp complex subjects without the necessary guidance and mentorship from their teachers. This lack of support hinders their ability to excel in both religious and modern subjects. To alleviate these challenges, a balanced and manageable curriculum should be designed, allowing students to excel in both religious and secular subjects. Additionally, creating a supportive and nurturing environment within Madrasahs, where teachers actively engage with students and provide guidance, is crucial for their academic development.

Focus on religious knowledge and lack of critical thinking

While the emphasis on religious knowledge is a fundamental aspect of Madrasah education, it often comes at the expense of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Qawmi Madrasahs, in particular, focus predominantly on religious texts and memorization, leaving students with limited exposure to diverse perspectives and critical analysis. This lack of critical thinking skills can hinder students' adaptability in a rapidly changing world and limit their ability to engage in informed discourse on various subjects beyond religion. To ensure that Madrasah graduates are well-rounded individuals capable of contributing to society, it is essential to incorporate critical thinking and analytical skills into the curriculum. Integrating subjects that promote critical thinking, encouraging open discussions, and exposing students to a diverse range of ideas are essential steps in addressing this challenge. Moreover, professional development opportunities for teachers can enable them to foster critical thinking skills in their students effectively [18].

Curriculum formulation and lack of integration with mainstream education

The curriculum formulation in Madrasahs, particularly in Qawmi Madrasahs, is often independent of government guidelines or input from educationists. This autonomy in curriculum development can lead to disparities between Madrasah and mainstream education. While Alia Madrasahs follow a government-approved curriculum that integrates both religious and modern subjects, Qawmi Madrasahs continue to maintain a traditional curriculum with a heavy focus on religious knowledge. This lack of alignment with mainstream education can limit students' opportunities for higher education and employment outside the religious sector. To bridge this gap, there is a need for greater collaboration between Madrasah authorities, government agencies, and education experts. This collaboration can lead to the development of a curriculum that not only imparts religious knowledge but also equips students with the skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in a diverse and competitive world. In conclusion, addressing these educational challenges in Madrasahs is critical to ensuring that students receive a well-rounded education that prepares them for success in both religious and secular domains. By reforming the curriculum, enhancing teacher training, and promoting critical thinking, Madrasah education

in Bangladesh can better equip its graduates for the challenges of the modern world [19].

2.2 Government involvement and policies

In the context of Madrasah education in Bangladesh, government involvement and policies play a pivotal role in shaping the landscape and addressing the challenges faced by these institutions. There are two main categories of Madrasahs in Bangladesh, each subject to different regulatory frameworks: Alia Madrasahs, which operate within state-defined parameters, and Qawmi Madrasahs, which are privately run and associated with various religious associations. This section explores the government's role in regulating these institutions, the controversies surrounding recognition and equivalence, and the broader implications of these policies [20].

State-defined parameters for Alia Madrasahs

Alia Madrasahs in Bangladesh operate within a regulatory framework defined by the state. These institutions offer a curriculum that integrates both religious and modern subjects, aiming to provide students with a balanced education. The government's involvement in the regulation of Alia Madrasahs extends to curriculum approval, teacher recruitment, and the issuance of certificates. One of the key advantages of Alia Madrasahs is their adherence to government-approved curricula. This alignment ensures that students receive an education that meets national standards and allows them to pursue higher education in mainstream institutions. Additionally, the government conducts Teachers' Registration Examinations to ensure that Alia Madrasah teachers meet specific qualification criteria. However, challenges persist in the implementation of these policies. Despite the alignment with government curricula, the quality of instruction in modern subjects, such as Mathematics and English, remains a concern. The shortage of well-trained teachers for these subjects and a lack of modern teaching resources hinder the effectiveness of Alia Madrasah education [1].

Privately run Qawmi Madrasahs and their associations

Qawmi Madrasahs, in contrast, operate under private management and do not adhere to government-defined parameters or curricula. These institutions are affiliated with various religious associations and maintain a strong degree of autonomy in shaping their educational programs. Qawmi Madrasahs primarily focus on religious knowledge and Islamic studies. The lack of government regulation over Qawmi Madrasahs has sparked debates and concerns about the quality of education and the alignment of their curricula with the needs of modern society. These institutions receive funds from both internal and foreign sources, raising questions about transparency and potential links to external actors involved in terrorism financing. This unregulated financial aspect has been a subject of scrutiny, and calls for greater oversight have been made. Additionally, Qawmi Madrasahs' autonomy in curriculum formulation has led to disparities between their educational offerings and those of Alia Madrasahs and mainstream educational institutions. This lack of alignment can limit the opportunities available to Qawmi Madrasah graduates, particularly in terms of higher education and employment prospects outside the religious sector [9].

Controversies surrounding recognition and equivalence

A significant controversy in the realm of Madrasah education in Bangladesh revolves around the recognition and equivalence of Madrasah degrees with those from mainstream institutions. The most contentious recognition was that of the Qawmi Madrasah's Dawra degree as equivalent to a Master's Degree from a university. The decision to recognize the Dawra degree at the level of a Master's Degree was met with criticism and debate. Critics argued that this equivalence did not address the need for syllabus upgrading or content reform in Qawmi Madrasahs. They expressed concerns about the potential devaluation of higher education degrees and the lack of alignment between Qawmi Madrasah curricula and modern educational standards. The controversy over equivalence highlights the challenges of integrating Madrasah education into the broader academic and professional landscape of Bangladesh. It underscores the need for comprehensive reform efforts that address both curriculum content and the quality of instruction. In conclusion, government involvement and policies in Madrasah education in Bangladesh are essential for regulating and standardizing these institutions. While Alia Madrasahs benefit from state-defined parameters and curricula, challenges persist in terms of ensuring the quality of modern education. On the other hand, Qawmi Madrasahs operate with a high degree of autonomy, raising concerns about curriculum alignment and financial transparency. The controversy over recognition and equivalence further underscores the need for comprehensive reform efforts to bridge the gaps in Madrasah education and ensure that graduates are well-prepared for the challenges of the modern world.

2.3 Socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh

Madrasahs in Bangladesh have a profound socio-political impact, serving as a symbolic manifestation of the relationship between political regimes and religious groups. The history, influence, and controversies surround-

ing Madrasah education in the country reveal a complex web of socio-political dynamics that have far-reaching consequences. In this section, we delve into the multifaceted socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh, shedding light on their significance in shaping the nation's identity and political landscape.

Historical Significance and Political Patronage

Madrasahs in Bangladesh have a long and storied history that dates back centuries. They have served as centers of Islamic learning and religious instruction, contributing to the preservation and dissemination of Islamic knowledge. Over time, Madrasahs gained prominence in society and attracted students from various backgrounds, including those from economically disadvantaged families. One of the most striking aspects of the socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh is the patronage they receive from political regimes. Governments have historically sought the support of religious groups and institutions, including Madrasahs, to bolster their political standing. This patronage often involves providing financial support and other incentives to Madrasahs, which, in turn, can influence the political allegiance of religious leaders and their followers. The interplay between political regimes and Madrasahs has shaped the socio-political landscape in Bangladesh. It highlights the delicate balance between secularism and religious influence in the country's politics. While Madrasahs are instrumental in educating students in matters of faith and religion, their alignment with political agendas can lead to polarization and tensions within society.

Polarization and Religious Extremism

The socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh is not without its challenges. One significant concern is the potential for polarization and the emergence of religious extremism. While the majority of Madrasahs in Bangladesh adhere to moderate and traditional interpretations of Islam, there have been instances of radicalization among a minority of students. The influence of a small number of Madrasahs that promote radical ideologies has raised alarms in both domestic and international contexts. These institutions are often associated with extremist activities and have been a focal point in the government's efforts to counter religious extremism. The socio-political implications of such radicalization are far-reaching and include security concerns, potential social unrest, and damage to Bangladesh's international image. The complex interplay between Madrasahs, political patronage, and extremism underscores the need for effective oversight and regulation to mitigate potential risks. Striking a balance between preserving religious freedom and countering extremism remains a significant challenge for policymakers.

The Role of Madrasahs in Political Movements

Madrasahs have played a notable role in various political movements and protests in Bangladesh. Their ability to mobilize students and religious leaders has made them a potent force in advocating for specific political and social causes. One notable example is the association of some Madrasahs with the controversial Hefazat-e-Islam movement, which has been involved in protests and demands for stricter Islamic governance. The involvement of Madrasahs in political movements reflects their influence in shaping public discourse and mobilizing segments of the population. It also highlights the diversity of perspectives within the Madrasah community, ranging from moderate to conservative and even radical viewpoints. The political engagement of Madrasahs underscores their significance in influencing the socio-political landscape of Bangladesh.

Challenges to Secularism and Religious Pluralism

The socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh extends to the country's secularism and religious pluralism. While Bangladesh has a secular constitution, the presence and influence of Madrasahs raise questions about the extent to which religious values should shape public policies and governance. Some argue that the socio-political influence of Madrasahs can challenge the secular and pluralistic principles enshrined in the country's constitution. The push for stricter interpretations of Islamic law and the role of religious leaders in shaping public opinion can create tensions between secular and religious forces. At the same time, Madrasahs contribute to the religious pluralism of Bangladesh by providing education to students from diverse religious backgrounds. They offer a space for interfaith dialogue and understanding, fostering a sense of religious tolerance among students. In conclusion, the socio-political impact of Madrasahs in Bangladesh is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. These institutions have historical significance and play a vital role in shaping the nation's identity and political landscape. While they contribute to religious education and pluralism, challenges such as political patronage, radicalization, and tensions with secularism underscore the need for thoughtful regulation and dialogue to ensure a harmonious coexistence of religious and secular values in Bangladesh's socio-political arena.

3 Comparative Analysis

3.1 Curriculum development in Alia Madrasahs

Government-approved curriculum

Alia Madrasahs in Bangladesh offer a unique blend of religious and modern education. One of the key aspects of their curriculum development is the incorporation of a government-approved curriculum for modern education. This distinguishes them from Qawmi Madrasahs, which primarily focus on religious knowledge. The government's involvement in shaping the curriculum for Alia Madrasahs reflects a commitment to providing students with a well-rounded education that includes modern subjects. The curriculum encompasses a range of subjects, including mathematics, science, social studies, and languages, in addition to religious subjects. This approach aligns with the broader educational goals of Bangladesh, emphasizing the importance of equipping students with the skills and knowledge needed to participate in the modern workforce. Despite the government's efforts to integrate modern subjects into the curriculum, there are challenges and areas for improvement. For instance, the quality of instruction and resources for modern subjects in Alia Madrasahs needs enhancement. Many of these institutions face limitations in terms of science equipment, practical training labs, and well-trained teachers for modern subjects, which hinders the effectiveness of modern education.

Integration of religious and specialized subjects

One of the strengths of Alia Madrasahs is their ability to provide students with a comprehensive education that combines religious knowledge with specialized subjects. In addition to core religious studies, Alia Madrasahs offer specialized subjects such as Arabic literature, Hadith, and the Quran. This integration allows students to gain in-depth knowledge of their faith while also developing expertise in specific areas of religious scholarship. The curriculum of Alia Madrasahs is carefully designed to ensure a balance between religious and modern education. This approach acknowledges the importance of religious literacy in Bangladesh's predominantly Muslim population while also preparing students for academic and professional pursuits. It allows graduates to pursue higher studies in both religious and secular disciplines, offering them a range of career opportunities. While the integration of religious and specialized subjects is a commendable feature of Alia Madrasahs, it is essential to continually review and update these curricula to keep pace with changing educational needs and global developments. The challenges lie in maintaining a high standard of instruction in both religious and modern subjects and ensuring that the curriculum remains relevant and engaging.

Challenges and areas for improvement

Despite the positive aspects of curriculum development in Alia Madrasahs, there are several challenges and areas for improvement. These include:

- **Quality of Instruction:** While the curriculum may encompass a wide range of subjects, the quality of instruction in modern subjects, such as mathematics and science, needs enhancement. Alia Madrasahs often face resource constraints and a shortage of well-qualified teachers for these subjects. To bridge this gap, investments in teacher training, provision of science equipment, and the establishment of practical training labs are essential.
- **Science and Technology Education:** With the growing importance of science and technology in the modern world, there is a need to strengthen the science and technology education offered in Alia Madrasahs. This includes an emphasis on practical knowledge and hands-on learning experiences [21].
- **Curriculum Relevance:** The curriculum must remain relevant to the evolving needs of students and the job market. Continuous review and updates are necessary to align the curriculum with the demands of the modern workforce and higher education institutions.
- **Integration with Mainstream Education:** To ensure that Alia Madrasah graduates can seamlessly transition into mainstream education and the job market, there should be efforts to align the curriculum with national standards and promote recognition of Alia Madrasah qualifications.

In conclusion, the curriculum development in Alia Madrasahs represents a unique approach to education in Bangladesh. The integration of religious and specialized subjects, along with a government-approved curriculum for modern education, offers students a well-rounded education. However, addressing the challenges and areas for improvement is crucial to enhance the quality and relevance of education in Alia Madrasahs and empower graduates to thrive in both religious and modern academic disciplines.

3.2 Curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs

Qawmi Madrasahs in Bangladesh are known for their unwavering commitment to religious education. Unlike Alia Madrasahs, which integrate modern subjects into their curriculum, Qawmi Madrasahs have a singular focus on religious knowledge. This emphasis on religious education is the cornerstone of their curriculum, and it permeates every aspect of their academic and extracurricular activities. The curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs places a strong emphasis on the Quran, Hadith (the sayings and actions of Prophet Muhammad(S.A.W.)), Islamic jurisprudence, and other theological subjects. Students devote a significant portion of their time to memorizing and reciting the Quran, delving into the intricacies of Islamic law, and developing a deep understanding of religious principles. This educational approach aligns with the mission of Qawmi Madrasahs to produce individuals well-versed in Islamic teachings and traditions.

One of the distinctive features of Qawmi Madrasahs is the absence of integration with non-religious subjects. Unlike Alia Madrasahs, which provide students with a balanced education that includes modern subjects like mathematics, science, and social studies, Qawmi Madrasahs do not incorporate these subjects into their curriculum. This lack of integration results in a curriculum that is solely focused on religious knowledge, with little exposure to non-religious disciplines. While this approach fulfills the goal of Qawmi Madrasahs to produce individuals deeply rooted in Islamic scholarship, it has implications for students' preparedness for the modern world. Graduates of Qawmi Madrasahs may find themselves lacking the skills and knowledge needed to excel in fields beyond religious studies. This lack of integration can limit their socioeconomic mobility and career opportunities, particularly in a rapidly changing and competitive job market. Furthermore, since Qawmi Madrasahs do not adhere to the national curriculum, there is a distinct lack of alignment with the broader educational framework of Bangladesh.

The curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs, with its exclusive focus on religious education, presents a series of challenges and implications:

- **Limited Skill Diversification:** Students in Qawmi Madrasahs may lack diversification in their skill set, having specialized predominantly in religious knowledge. The narrow focus on religious subjects may limit their adaptability to different academic and professional contexts.
- **Socioeconomic Constraints:** The absence of integration with non-religious subjects can hinder graduates' job prospects, particularly in fields that demand a modern educational background. This can contribute to a higher rate of unemployment among Qawmi Madrasah graduates.
- **Need for Curriculum Reform:** The curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs may benefit from reform efforts aimed at diversifying students' knowledge base. Integrating modern subjects and enhancing the quality of instruction in these areas is crucial for the holistic development of students.
- **Socio-Political Considerations:** The strong emphasis on religious education has socio-political implications. It can shape the worldview of students and their role in society, particularly concerning the promotion of conservative Islamic values.

In summary, the curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs is centered on religious education, to the exclusion of non-religious subjects. While this approach aligns with their mission of producing Islamic scholars, it has implications for graduates' readiness to engage with the multifaceted demands of the contemporary world. Addressing these challenges and considering curriculum reform is paramount in ensuring that Qawmi Madrasah students are better prepared for a wider range of opportunities and challenges beyond the realm of religious education.

3.3 Disparities in English and Math/ICT education

One of the significant challenges faced by Qawmi Madrasah students in Bangladesh pertains to disparities in English, mathematics, and information and communication technology (ICT) education compared to students in mainstream educational institutions. These disparities carry considerable implications for students' skill development and their employability prospects. The focus on religious education in Qawmi Madrasahs means that subjects like English, mathematics, and ICT receive less attention. As a result, students graduating from these institutions often lag behind their counterparts from mainstream schools in these essential subjects. This imbalance limits their ability to compete effectively in the job market, where proficiency in these areas is highly valued. Employers frequently seek candidates with a strong command of English and mathematical skills, as well as ICT proficiency, which is increasingly important in today's technology-driven world. The disparity in these areas affects graduates' employability in various sectors, including government jobs and positions in the private sector. Qawmi Madrasah graduates, with their lack of expertise in English and mathematics, often struggle during job interviews, despite their deep religious knowledge.

Another significant implication of the disparities in English, mathematics, and ICT education in Qawmi Madrasahs is the limited exposure of students to the outside world. Students who receive a primarily religious education often lack the broader perspective and skills that come from engaging with subjects and technologies that are not covered in their curriculum. In an era where the internet and digital technologies play a pivotal role in connecting individuals with information and the global community, students with limited ICT exposure face challenges in accessing knowledge beyond their religious studies. This not only hinders their ability to keep up with the fast-paced global advancements but also limits their capacity to explore diverse perspectives and engage with the world beyond the boundaries of their curriculum.

3.4 Co-curricular education and extracurricular activities

One notable characteristic of Qawmi Madrasahs is the absence of co-curricular activities in their educational framework. While these institutions provide a strong foundation in religious knowledge, they often overlook the significance of co-curricular education, which is an integral part of holistic skill development in mainstream educational systems. Co-curricular activities encompass a wide range of experiences that extend beyond the traditional classroom setting. These activities include debates, sports, arts, and various clubs and societies, which play a pivotal role in nurturing students' interpersonal skills, leadership abilities, and creativity. Unfortunately, Qawmi Madrasahs typically do not incorporate these activities into their curriculum, potentially limiting students' overall growth and personal development. Moreover, Qawmi Madrasah students face limited opportunities to participate in national sports competitions and other extracurricular events. These activities not only contribute to students' physical well-being but also foster teamwork, discipline, and sportsmanship. However, students in these institutions often miss out on such experiences. While Alia Madrasahs may offer a more balanced blend of religious and modern education along with extracurricular activities, Qawmi Madrasahs, with their primary focus on religious knowledge, may inadvertently restrict students' participation in national sports competitions and other extracurricular events.

In conclusion, disparities in English, mathematics, and ICT education, coupled with the absence of co-curricular activities and limited exposure to national sports competitions, pose significant challenges for students in Qawmi Madrasahs. Addressing these disparities and providing a more well-rounded educational experience can contribute to better skill development and prepare students for a wider range of opportunities in their academic and professional lives.

4 Challenges and Future Prospects

4.1 Socioeconomic factors and student backgrounds

A fundamental challenge faced by Madrasahs in Bangladesh is the socioeconomic background of a significant proportion of their students. Madrasah education, especially in Qawmi Madrasahs, often attracts students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds. Many students come from poor and lower-middle-class families who struggle to provide for basic needs, let alone educational resources. This socioeconomic factor directly influences the quality of education students receive. Inadequate financial support often leads to resource constraints, outdated facilities, and limitations in the quality of education offered. The impact of this challenge is felt across multiple aspects of Madrasah education, including curriculum development, teacher quality, and overall student outcomes.

4.2 Stigma and marginalization of Madrasah graduates

Another significant challenge is the stigma and marginalization that Madrasah graduates often face in the job market and society at large. While Madrasahs produce individuals with deep religious knowledge, the focus on religious education often results in a lack of expertise in modern academic disciplines. This lack of expertise can lead to limited employment opportunities, as many employers require skills in areas such as English, mathematics, and ICT. As a result, a considerable percentage of Madrasah graduates, especially from Qawmi Madrasahs, find themselves unemployed or working in non-governmental Islamic organizations with a limited scope of employment.

4.3 Impact of heavy course loads and resource constraints

Heavy course loads, combined with resource constraints, constitute a major challenge in Madrasah education. The rigorous religious curriculum often leaves students with limited time and energy to explore other subjects that could enhance their overall skill set and employability. Resource constraints play a significant role in this

challenge, as many Madrasahs lack modern facilities and well-trained teachers for non-religious subjects. This results in students being unable to access the necessary resources and guidance to excel in areas like English, mathematics, and ICT.

4.4 Challenges in curriculum reform and content upgrading

Curriculum reform and content upgrading pose an essential challenge for Madrasah education. The traditional focus on religious knowledge, particularly in Qawmi Madrasahs, has led to an academic gap in subjects vital for modern life. Upgrading the curriculum to incorporate more English, mathematics, and ICT is crucial to better prepare students for a wide range of job opportunities. However, implementing such changes faces resistance from some quarters, concerned that modern education might lead students astray from their Islamic heritage. Striking a balance between religious and modern education remains a challenge, but it is essential to ensure that Madrasah graduates are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed in today's competitive job market.

4.5 Political history and implications for Madrasah education

The political history of Madrasahs in Bangladesh is intertwined with the socio-political landscape of the country. These institutions often serve as symbolic representations of political regimes' reliance on religious groups and the institutions they run. The complex relationship between religion, politics, and education creates both challenges and opportunities for Madrasah education. The controversies and debates surrounding Madrasah education's recognition and equivalence, as well as the financing of Qawmi Madrasahs, have significant political implications. The decisions made in this context can influence the future direction and prospects of Madrasah education in Bangladesh. In conclusion, the challenges faced by Madrasah education in Bangladesh are multifaceted, stemming from socioeconomic factors, curriculum limitations, resource constraints, and the complex interplay of religion and politics. Addressing these challenges will be vital in ensuring that Madrasah graduates are better prepared for a broader range of opportunities and that Madrasahs continue to serve as valuable educational institutions in the country's landscape.

5 Recommendation

5.1 Improving curriculum development in Alia Madrasahs

To bridge the existing educational gap between Alia Madrasahs and mainstream schools in Bangladesh, a fundamental step is to modernize the curriculum. While Alia Madrasahs already teach a government-approved curriculum, there is room for further enhancement to ensure that students receive a holistic education.

- **Modernization:** The existing curriculum can be modernized by incorporating subjects that are vital for today's global job market. This includes a more comprehensive focus on English, mathematics, and ICT. These subjects are essential for students to compete in various professions and industries. The curriculum should be updated to meet the requirements of the current global economy, ensuring that students graduate with relevant skills.
- **Quality Enhancement:** Quality improvement is equally important. This can be achieved through regular curriculum assessments, ensuring that the subjects are up to date and that students receive high-quality instruction. In particular, there is a need to enhance the science curriculum, providing students with a better understanding of modern scientific principles and fostering critical thinking skills.

To implement a modernized and high-quality curriculum effectively, a focus on teacher training and adequate resources is crucial. Alia Madrasahs should establish teacher training programs to prepare educators to deliver modern subjects effectively. Teachers need training not only in the content but also in teaching methods that engage students and encourage critical thinking. Specialized training programs should be created for subjects like English, mathematics, and ICT, ensuring that teachers are well-prepared to impart these skills to students. Adequate resources, including textbooks, science equipment, and practical training labs, should be provided to support the curriculum. Access to modern teaching materials is essential for students to grasp these subjects effectively. Additionally, well-equipped science and computer labs are vital to offer practical exposure and hands-on learning. An emphasis should also be placed on hiring well-trained teachers for modern subjects. These teachers should not only possess in-depth knowledge of their respective subjects but also be skilled in teaching and guiding students effectively. This will contribute significantly to narrowing the educational gap between Alia Madrasahs and mainstream schools. Incorporating modernization, quality enhancement, teacher training, and resource provision into the curriculum development process will help Alia Madrasahs prepare students for a broader range of educational and professional opportunities. These steps are essential to ensure

that Madrasah graduates are not only well-versed in religious knowledge but also equipped with the skills and knowledge needed in a competitive job market, enabling them to contribute effectively to the development of the country.

5.2 Curriculum reform in Qawmi Madrasahs

The curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs primarily focuses on religious education, leaving students with a significant gap in non-religious subjects such as mathematics, English, and ICT. To address this issue, it is imperative to integrate these subjects into the curriculum. This integration should be designed to provide students with a well-rounded education that equips them with the skills needed in the modern world. The skills gap among Qawmi Madrasah students, particularly in English, mathematics, and ICT, can be narrowed through curriculum reform. By introducing these subjects into the curriculum, Qawmi students will be better prepared to compete in a wide range of professions and industries. Addressing the skills gap is vital for their employability and overall academic growth.

5.3 Bridging the gap in English and Math/ICT proficiency

Innovative teaching methods can be employed to bridge the proficiency gap in English and Math/ICT. These methods should be tailored to the unique learning environment of Madrasahs and designed to engage students actively. Encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving in these subjects is crucial for overall skill development. Co-curricular activities are a valuable addition to the education system. Encouraging students to participate in activities such as debates, quizzes, and science exhibitions can significantly improve their English, mathematics, and ICT skills. These activities provide practical exposure and foster holistic development.

5.4 Government policies and support

Collaboration between government authorities and Madrasah administrations is essential for successful curriculum reform in Qawmi Madrasahs. By working together, these institutions can ensure that the integration of non-religious subjects is well-implemented and that the curriculum meets modern educational standards. Government policies should be designed to address the concerns of Qawmi Madrasahs, including their apprehension about the inclusion of non-religious subjects. Building trust and fostering a cooperative environment between the government and Qawmi authorities will be pivotal in implementing curriculum reforms successfully.

Reforming the curriculum in Qawmi Madrasahs, integrating non-religious subjects, addressing the skills gap, and bridging proficiency in English, mathematics, and ICT, require a comprehensive approach. Innovative teaching methods and co-curricular activities will empower students, while government policies and collaboration with Madrasah authorities will be vital for the success of these reforms. These efforts will help Qawmi students gain a more balanced and competitive education, enabling them to contribute effectively to the modern world.

6 Conclusion

In this comprehensive exploration of Madrasah education in Bangladesh, we have uncovered various facets of this dual system. The research delved into the distinct differences between Alia and Qawmi Madrasahs, the challenges they face, and the implications for students and society at large. We identified that Madrasah students are trailing behind in English, mathematics, and ICT compared to their mainstream counterparts. This skills gap is a result of a combination of factors, including a mismatch between the skills required and those available among Madrasah faculty, the weight of heavy course loads, and inadequate teacher support. It's noteworthy that these challenges have hindered Madrasah students' employability and overall proficiency in modern academic disciplines. A significant revelation was the limited integration of non-religious subjects in Qawmi Madrasahs. Their curriculum primarily focuses on religious education, leaving students ill-equipped to navigate the complexities of a modern, competitive world. Their isolation from the outside world, due to restrictions on reading material and interactions, compounds this challenge. However, Alia Madrasahs, with their government-approved curriculum and blended approach to religious and specialized subjects, are relatively better positioned to prepare students for a broader range of opportunities. Still, they encounter issues such as resource constraints, deteriorating infrastructure, and diminishing enrolment.

The future of Madrasah education in Bangladesh is at a crossroads. With the current state of affairs, there is a pressing need for reforms to ensure that these institutions can meet the demands of the contemporary world. The challenges we've highlighted indicate that a failure to adapt and evolve may result in Madrasah students being left behind, unable to compete effectively in the job market or to contribute to society's growth.

For Qawmi Madrasahs, the reluctance to incorporate non-religious subjects and modern teaching methodologies is particularly concerning. Their refusal to evolve may lead to further isolation, diminishing the scope of opportunities for their students. To secure a more prosperous future, these Madrasahs should seriously consider adopting a more balanced and inclusive approach to education. On the other hand, Alia Madrasahs must tackle issues such as resource constraints, infrastructure, and teacher quality to deliver a high-quality modern and religious education. Without these improvements, their contribution to society may diminish, with fewer students opting for Alia Madrasahs. The future of Madrasah education hinges on the willingness of all stakeholders, including Madrasah authorities, the government, and the broader society, to adapt, innovate, and reform.

Curriculum development is the linchpin for enhancing Madrasah education in Bangladesh. The curriculum must strike a balance between religious and modern subjects to equip students with the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in an ever-evolving world. For Alia Madrasahs, continuing to provide a unified education with religious knowledge and specialized subjects is a positive step. However, there is a need for significant investment in modernization and infrastructure to ensure quality education. For Qawmi Madrasahs, the most critical challenge is the lack of integration with non-religious subjects. This issue should be addressed with an open-minded approach that prepares students for a wider spectrum of opportunities. In both cases, the curriculum should promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and a deeper understanding of diverse subjects, making students more adaptable in the job market and society. In conclusion, Madrasah education in Bangladesh stands at a pivotal juncture. Curriculum development and reform are the need of the hour. For Madrasahs to thrive and continue to play a vital role in the education landscape of Bangladesh, they must evolve, adapt, and embrace the changing educational needs and aspirations of their students and society. By doing so, they can ensure a brighter future for the next generation of Madrasah students, enabling them to become active contributors to the nation's progress.

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